

Mercury seen from Mars (local Extrema of apparent brightness from 1975-1983)

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An observer stays in a space ship that circles round the Mars.

Explanations: mag = stellar magnitude, °=degree, ' = angular minute, " = angular second

AE= astronomical unit =149598500 km

Date	apparent brightness [mag]	Phase in per cent	Distance of Mercury from Mars [AE]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	apparent diameter ["]	Distance of Mercury to Sun [AE]
1.1.1975	+0.78	41	1.40	16.21	4.8	0.43
27.1.-30.1.1975	-0.94	99-100 decreasing	1.79-1.80 decreasing	0.93-1.83 increasing	3.7-3.8 increasing	0.31
23.3.1975	weaker than +7.00	<1	0.98	2.02	6.8	0.45
29.4.-1.5.1975	-0.92	93-98 increasing	1.65-1.70 increasing	3.84-6.38 increasing	3.9-4.1 decreasing	0.30-0.32 increasing
8.7.1975	weaker than +7.00	<1	1.02	1.52-1.53 increasing	6.6	0.37
30.7.-2.8.1975	-0.71	78-87 increasing	1.55-1.63 increasing	9.34-10.85 decreasing	4.1-4.4 decreasing	0.32-0.34 increasing
15.10.1975	weaker than +8.00	<1	1.16	0.08	5.8	0.31
3.11.-6.11.1975	-0.16	68-77 increasing	1.59-1.68 increasing	12.27-12.93 decreasing	3.9-4.2 decreasing	0.36-0.38 increasing
1.12.-6.12.1975	+0.20	99-100 decreasing	2.00	0.77-2.19 increasing	3.3	0.46-0.47 decreasing
28.12.-30.12.1975	-0.05	72-78 decreasing	1.70-1.75 decreasing	11.78-12.21 increasing	3.8-3.9 increasing	0.37-0.39 decreasing
19.1.1976	weaker than +7.50	<1	1.28	0.99	5.2	0.31
31.3.-3.4.1976	-0.28	78-87 decreasing	1.82-1.90 decreasing	8.28-9.58 increasing	3.5-3.7 increasing	0.33-0.35 decreasing
24.4.1976	weaker than +7.00	<1	1.32	1.33	5.1	0.34
2.7.-4.7.1976	-0.53	87-94 decreasing	1.88-1.93 decreasing	5.71-7.20 increasing	3.4-3.6 increasing	0.31-0.33 decreasing
30.7.1976	weaker than +8.00	<1	1.25	1.09	5.3	0.40
1.10.-3.10.1976	-0.78	95-99 decreasing	1.86-1.89 decreasing	2.72-4.50 increasing	3.5-3.6 increasing	0.30-0.32 decreasing
11.11.1976	weaker than +10.00	<1	1.08	0.31	6.2	0.46
1.1.-3.1.1977	-0.97	99-100 increasing	1.77	0.76-1.51 decreasing	3.8	0.31
28.2.1977	weaker than +7.00	<1	0.97	2.20	6.9	0.44
3.4.-4.4.1977	-0.96	91-96 increasing	1.63-1.67 increasing	5.46-7.05 decreasing	4.0-4.1 decreasing	0.31-0.32 increasing
13.6.-14.6.1977	weaker than +7.00	<1	1.04-1.05 increasing	1.19-1.21 decreasing	6.3-6.4 decreasing	0.35
4.7.-7.7.1977	-0.62	76-85 increasing	1.55-1.63 increasing	10.08-11.39 decreasing	4.1-4.3 decreasing	0.32-0.34 increasing
13.8.-18.8.1977	+0.16	85-91 decreasing	1.74-1.81 decreasing	10.82-12.83 increasing	3.7-3.9 increasing	0.45-0.47 decreasing
21.8.-28.8.1977	+0.14	67-80 decreasing	1.56-1.69 decreasing	14.11-15.45 increasing	4.0-4.3 increasing	0.41-0.45 decreasing
20.9.1977	weaker than +7.00	<1	1.19	0.31	5.6	0.31
10.10.-11.10.1977	-0.05	70-74 increasing	1.63-1.67 increasing	12.86-13.09 decreasing	4.0-4.1 decreasing	0.37-0.39 increasing

2.11.-9.11.1977	+0.22	98-100 increasing	2.00-2.03 increasing	0.75-3.69 decreasing	3.3-3.4 decreasing	0.47
1.12.-5.12.1977	-0.09	72-81 decreasing	1.72-1.80 decreasing	10.87-11.72 increasing	3.7-3.9 increasing	0.36-0.38 decreasing
24.12.1977	weaker than +7.50	<1	1.30	1.09	5.1	0.32
6.3.-8.3.1978	-0.33	81-87 decreasing	1.84-1.90 decreasing	7.98-8.96 increasing	3.5-3.6 increasing	0.33-0.35 decreasing
30.3.1978	weaker than +7.50	<1	1.32	1.33-1.34 increasing	5.1	0.35
6.6.-8.6.1978	-0.58	90-94 decreasing	1.88-1.93 decreasing	5.36-6.60 increasing	3.4-3.6 increasing	0.31-0.33 decreasing
6.7.-7.7.1978	weaker than +8.00	<1	1.21-1.22 decreasing	0.93-0.94 increasing	5.5	0.41-0.42 increasing
5.9.-8.9.1978	-0.82	96-100 decreasing	1.84-1.88 decreasing	1.68-4.17 increasing	3.5-3.7 increasing	0.30-0.32 decreasing
19.10.1978	weaker than +10.00	<1	1.04	0.73-0.74 increasing	6.4	0.46-0.47 increasing
7.12.-8.12.1978	-0.99	99-100 increasing	1.74-1.76 increasing	0.89-2.30 decreasing	3.8-3.9 decreasing	0.30-0.31 increasing
6.2.1979	weaker than +7.00	<1	0.97-0.98 increasing	2.22-2.24 decreasing	6.8-6.9 decreasing	0.42-0.43 decreasing
8.3.-10.3.1979	-0.92	88-95 increasing	1.60-1.66 increasing	6.30-8.33 decreasing	4.0-4.2 decreasing	0.31-0.32 increasing
21.5.1979	weaker than +7.00	<1	1.07	0.86-0.87 decreasing	6.2	0.33-0.34 decreasing
9.6.-12.6.1979	-0.52	73-83 increasing	1.55-1.64 increasing	10.68-11.86 decreasing	4.1-4.3 decreasing	0.33-0.35 increasing
16.7.-20.7.1979	+0.16	91-95 decreasing	1.83-1.88 decreasing	8.15-10.05 increasing	3.5-3.7 increasing	0.46-0.47 decreasing
30.7.-5.8.1979	+0.10	67-79 decreasing	1.58-1.70 decreasing	13.68-14.68 increasing	3.9-4.3 increasing	0.40-0.43 decreasing
26.8.1979	weaker than +8.00	<1	1.22	0.51	5.5	0.31
14.9.-18.9.1979	+0.07	66-77 increasing	1.63-1.73 increasing	12.82-13.53 decreasing	3.9-4.1 decreasing	0.38-0.41 increasing
5.10.-12.10.1979	+0.25	96-100 increasing	1.99-2.05 increasing	2.53-5.98 decreasing	3.3-3.4 decreasing	0.46-0.47 increasing
7.11.-9.11.1979	-0.14	76-80 decreasing	1.76-1.80 decreasing	10.55-10.94 increasing	3.7-3.8 increasing	0.35-0.37 decreasing
29.11.1979	weaker than +7.00	<1	1.31	1.17-1.19 increasing	5.1	0.32
9.2.-10.2.1980	-0.38	84-87 decreasing	1.87-1.90 decreasing	7.82-8.22 increasing	3.5-3.6 increasing	0.33-0.34 decreasing
4.3.-5.3.1980	weaker than +7.00	<1	1.30-1.31 decreasing	1.32-1.33 increasing	5.1-5.2 increasing	0.36-0.37 increasing
11.5.-12.5.1980	-0.63	92-95 decreasing	1.89-1.92 decreasing	5.02-5.92 increasing	3.5-3.6 increasing	0.31-0.32 decreasing
12.6.1980	weaker than +9.50	<1	1.19	0.73-0.74 increasing	5.6	0.42
10.8.-13.8.1980	-0.86	97-100 decreasing	1.82-1.86 decreasing	0.85-3.61 increasing	3.6-3.7 increasing	0.30-0.32 decreasing
26.9.1980	weaker than +9.00	<1	1.02	1.19	6.6	0.47
10.11.-12.11.1980	-1.00	98-100 increasing	1.72-1.74 increasing	1.91-3.29 decreasing	3.8-3.9 decreasing	0.30-0.31 increasing
13.1.-14.1.1981	weaker than +6.50	<1	0.98-0.99 increasing	2.11-2.12 decreasing	6.7-6.9 decreasing	0.40-0.41 decreasing
9.2.-12.2.1981	-0.87	85-92 increasing	1.58-1.65 increasing	7.36-9.24 decreasing	4.0-4.2 decreasing	0.31-0.33 increasing
25.4.1981	weaker than +7.00	<1	1.10	0.54-0.55 decreasing	6.1	0.31-0.32 decreasing
15.5.-17.5.1981	-0.42	74-79 increasing	1.58-1.62 increasing	11.57-12.03 decreasing	4.1-4.3 decreasing	0.34-0.36 increasing
16.6.-24.6.1981	-0.16	94-99 decreasing	1.88-1.94 decreasing	4.61-8.40 increasing	3.4-3.6 increasing	0.45-0.47 decreasing
7.7.-10.7.1981	+0.05	70-76 decreasing	1.63-1.69 decreasing	13.34-13.81 increasing	3.9-4.1 increasing	0.39-0.41 decreasing

31.7.1981	weaker than +7.50	<1	1.24	0.69	5.4	0.31
22.8.-23.8.1981	+0.17	70-73 increasing	1.69-1.72 increasing	13.41-13.62 decreasing	3.9-4.1 decreasing	0.40-0.41 increasing
9.9.-12.9.1981	+0.29	95-97 increasing	2.00-2.03 increasing	5.80-7.25 decreasing	3.3-3.4 decreasing	0.46-0.47 increasing
12.10.-15.10.1981	-0.18	75-84 decreasing	1.77-1.85 decreasing	9.64-10.61 increasing	3.6-3.8 increasing	0.34-0.37 decreasing
3.11.-4.11.1981	weaker than +6.50	<1	1.32	1.24-1.25 increasing	5.1	0.33
13.1.-16.1.1982	-0.42	83-91 decreasing	1.86-1.93 decreasing	6.72-8.28 increasing	3.4-3.6 increasing	0.32-0.34 decreasing
8.2.1982	weaker than +8.00	<1	1.29	1.28-1.29 increasing	5.2	0.37-0.38 increasing
15.4.-18.4.1982	-0.67	91-98 decreasing	1.87-1.93 decreasing	3.72-6.08 increasing	3.4-3.6 increasing	0.31-0.32 decreasing
19.5.1982	weaker than +9.50	<1	1.16	0.48-0.49 increasing	5.8	0.44
15.7.-18.7.1982	-0.90	98-100 decreasing	1.81-1.83 decreasing	0.29-2.74 increasing	3.7	0.30-0.31 decreasing
4.9.1982	weaker than +8.00	<1	0.99	1.60-1.61 decreasing	6.8	0.46
15.10.-17.10.1982	-1.00	96-99 decreasing	1.69-1.72 increasing	2.98-4.44 decreasing	3.9-4.0 decreasing	0.30-0.32 increasing
22.12.1982	weaker than +6.50	<1	0.99-1.00 increasing	1.89-1.90 decreasing	6.7-6.8 decreasing	0.38-0.39 decreasing
15.1.-17.1.1983	-0.81	83-89 increasing	1.58-1.63 increasing	8.58-9.81 decreasing	4.1-4.3 decreasing	0.31-0.33 increasing
1.4.1983	weaker than +8.50	<1	1.13	0.25	5.9	0.32
20.4.-23.4.1983	-0.30	69-80 increasing	1.56-1.66 increasing	11.64-12.61 decreasing	4.0-4.3 decreasing	0.34-0.37 increasing
22.5.-25.5.1983	+0.18	98-100 decreasing	1.95-1.97 decreasing	3.24-4.77 increasing	3.4	0.46-0.47 decreasing
13.6.-16.6.1983	+0.01	69-79 decreasing	1.65-1.74 decreasing	12.41-13.17 increasing	3.8-4.1 increasing	0.38-0.41 decreasing
6.7.1983	weaker than +7.00	<1	1.26	0.83-0.84 increasing	5.3	0.31
29.7.-31.7.1983	+0.27	70-74 increasing	1.72-1.76 increasing	13.53-13.84 decreasing	3.8-3.9 decreasing	0.41-0.43 increasing
9.8.-18.8.1983	+0.32	87-96 increasing	1.92-2.03 increasing	6.84-10.72 decreasing	3.3-3.5 decreasing	0.45-0.47 increasing
17.9.-19.9.1983	-0.23	78-83 decreasing	1.81-1.85 decreasing	9.36-9.90 increasing	3.6-3.7 increasing	0.34-0.36 decreasing
10.10.1983	weaker than +7.00	<1	1.32	1.29-1.30 increasing	5.1	0.33
19.12.-21.12.1983	-0.47	85-92 decreasing	1.87-1.93 decreasing	6.35-7.75 increasing	3.4-3.6 increasing	0.32-0.33 decreasing

Made with STELLARIUM and PLANETARIUM.